

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

Doi: [10.15497/RDA00093](https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00093)

RDA for Persistent Identifiers

Celebrating A Decade of Data
RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop

Version: May 2023

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

The community cross-fertilisation workshop, 'RDA for Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)' brought chairs and members of RDA Working Groups (WGs) and Interest Groups (IGs) together, with members of the wider research data community to share and discuss challenges, solutions and initiatives associated with PIDs. This workshop was a collaboration with the [Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\)](#), with [Matthias Liffers](#) (Research Data Specialist, Informatics; ARDC) as guest co-host. The key findings of the workshop summarised herein will be used to direct the future strategy of the RDA community. Read more about the [community cross-fertilisation workshop series](#) in commemoration of the [RDA's 10th Anniversary](#).

CHALLENGES TO BE ADDRESSED WITHIN THE THEME OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS

Technology and interoperability

- Addressing and overcoming technical barriers e.g. i) differentiation between tools and instruments in the context of PID creation and use; ii) enabling and enhancing interoperability among tools / e-infrastructure leveraging PIDs and metadata; iii) ensuring a PID is universally unique; iv) domain / context dependencies in which single solutions would constrain and reduce interoperability.
- Inclusion of PIDs in workflows and the provenance record; needs to be balanced with allowing for PID absence / opt-out.
- Existing RDA outputs and recommendations go out of date quickly due to fast paced ICT and research data management development.
- Identifying and acceptance of responsibilities for link maintenance and functional landing pages.
- Defining "persistence" in different contexts.
- Balancing the cost considerations of evolving infrastructure with the need to provide a basis for sustainable use as PID uptake accelerates.

Infrastructure for adoption and sustainability

- Sustainability is needed to ensure adoption - open scholarly infrastructures require long-term commitment and support.
- The need to raise awareness of the value of widely adopting PIDs and integrating rich metadata, e.g. time / effort saving; applications.
- Promotion of PIDs work is needed to facilitate knowledge exchange and group involvement.
- A well-maintained repository of information is needed to understand the broader PID picture.
- Coordinated group collaboration is essential, with someone taking responsibility for this.
- PID adoption across disciplines and communities is needed to understand different perspectives and develop interoperability solutions.
- Achieving expansion of adoption and inclusivity into new regions (e.g. Global South).

PARTICIPATING GROUPS & WORKSHOP LEADS*

National PID Strategy WG
Nominated lead: [Christopher Brown](#)

- Outputs and achievements:
- *National PID Strategy Guide*
 - *National PID Strategy Checklist*
 - *Nine case studies collected*

See [community group card](#)

PID IG
Nominated lead(s): [Jonathan Clark](#)

- Outputs and achievements:
- *Consistently well attended Plenary sessions since 2013.*
 - *Hosted collaborations of RDA groups working on PIDs, incl. organisations, samples, PID types, equipment, projects.*

See [community group card](#)

Working with PIDs in Tools IG
Nominated lead: [Rory Macneil](#)

- Outputs and achievements:
- *EOSC RDA project: [Enhancing interoperability through use of PIDs in research platforms](#).*
 - *Jens Klump et al, [IGSN 2040 Technical Model](#).*

See [community group card](#)

*Workshop leads collected challenges, solutions and initiatives in preparation for the workshop and explained them during the workshop on behalf of their group.

Strategy and governance frameworks

- There is a lack of conversation on global PID strategies and communication of the value proposition for identifiers on a national level.
- Voluntary work is a limitation for working groups - resourced efforts are needed.
- There is a need to i) establish governance frameworks to progress the PID agenda; ii) involve all stakeholders; and iii) update / maintain PID services.
- Producing a national PID strategy requires funding and securing the commitment of governments and funders to develop, support and implement a PID strategy.

SOLUTIONS TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES

Strategy and governance frameworks

- Develop National PID Strategies and Roadmaps; encourage openness and sharing with these initiatives and capture lessons learnt.
- Communication is a key piece for national PID strategies; connection of people and promotion of the value proposition of identifiers starts with national coordination. Bring the conversations together through international coordination.
- National funders need to take strategic ownership and commit resources to communication and promotion, emphasising the central role of PIDs in advancing openness and FAIRness of research.
- In developing PID policy, actors with a role in implementing support for PID deployment should be involved, in particular research institutions and research tool developers.

Incentivisation and adoption

- A planned approach is needed to i) engage users from different contexts and disciplines to identify problems, issues and solutions; ii) coordinate discussions between RDA WGs / IGs, and non-RDA groups; iii) encourage engagement from non-experts on communication platforms; and iv) bring both institutions and researchers into the conversation.
- International initiatives for encouraging the gathering and presentation of information.
- Normalise PID workflows to be an integral part of research supporting tools and services.
- Involve users in the design of identifier systems.

Community and resources

- Revise and update PID related RDA recommendations and outputs.
- Develop common vocabularies between PID providers and interoperability infrastructure for object self-description.
- Create a PID Community of Practice to encourage neutral interaction and discussion within the global practitioners' community.
- Leverage existing groups and expertise e.g. RDA, and look for opportunities early.
- RDA involvement: more WGs / IGs and more co-chairs for RDA WGs and IGs
- Foster global knowledge-sharing and community building across disciplines; be especially inclusive of the Global South.
- More community building events and outreach activities to drive innovation and produce valuable outputs to address national challenges.

INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST

The following is a (non-exhaustive) selection of PID related initiatives, forums, projects and organisations.

Forums and projects

- [FAIR Digital Object Forum](#) - overlapping topics e.g. what metadata should be present at the PID "registry level" to facilitate machine actionability.
- [DFG-funded](#) project (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft): [PID Network Germany](#)
- Community groups e.g. [Research Data Alliance](#) and RDA projects e.g. [RDA Tiger](#)
- [Open Research Funders Group](#): actively working towards a shared understanding among funding organisations and institutions around PIDs and their role in FAIR outputs.
- [Implementing FAIR Workflows project](#): focuses on using PIDs and metadata in all stages of the research lifecycle. See the [workflows specification document](#). Guides for funders and researchers will also be shared through the project.

PID Providers and services:

- [Crossref](#), [DataCite](#), [ORCID](#), [ROR](#), [ISNI](#), [RAiD](#); [Africa PID Alliance](#), [DOI Foundation](#), [ISO](#)
 - BetterTogether Webinar series: Crossref, DataCite and ORCID [resources on Zenodo](#)
 - DataCite Global Access [Programme](#)
- [National Information Standards Organization \(NISO\)](#): host the PID Forum.

Organisations and industries

- Globally impactful organisations where PIDs are a key element in infrastructure ([EOSC](#), [OpenAIRE](#))
- Internet of Things industry

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY

Gather use cases on PID applications; make available in an easy to discover location to understand the global picture of activity around PIDs.

Share success stories on interactions between RDA WGs and IGs and researchers, funders and academic communities (non-RDA).

Identify communications experts and/or community managers to communicate the value of PIDs.

Creation of an RDA IG or Community of Practice focussing in information exchange about PIDs, possibly with [RDA Tiger](#) support.

Facilitation of further working group discussions.

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To become a member of the RDA, register [here](#).